

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2

Participant 1413

24 analogs of CACHE_1413_19 were submitted for round 2.
 2 compounds, including re-supplied parent molecule showed weak binding profile.

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1413_19

$K_D = 10 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 62% binding
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 %inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 40$

CACHE2-HO_1413_1

K_D (3% DMSO) = 82 μM (does not reach saturation) –
 207% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@50 μM)
 %inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 20$

CACHE2-HO_1413_3

$K_D = 20 \mu\text{M}$ – 32% binding
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 11$

Tested analogs

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1413_19

$K_D = 10 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 62% binding

DLS (solub@200 μM)

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 40$

<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1413_5 CACHE_1413_19 0.407</p>				
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1413_10 CACHE_1413_19 0.4702</p>				
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1413_15 CACHE_1413_19 0.517</p>				

Tested analogs (cont...)

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1413_19

$K_D = 10 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 62% binding

DLS (solub@200 μM)

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 40

 CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai CACHE2-HO_1413_25 CACHE_1413_19 0.5636				
 CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai CACHE2-HO_1413_29 CACHE_1413_19 0.6069				

15 analogs of CACHE_1413_21 were submitted for round 2.
 1 compound (re-supplied parent molecule) confirmed binding by SPR, showing the tendency to reach saturation.

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1413_21

$K_D = 11 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 74% binding
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 3

CACHE2-HO_1413_30

$K_D = 11 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 46% binding
 DLS (solub@50 μM)
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 3

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1413_21

$K_D = 11 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 74% binding

DLS (solub@200 μM)

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 3

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1413_34 Parent: CACHE_1413_21 distance_to_pai: 0.3594</p>				
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1413_39 Parent: CACHE_1413_21 distance_to_pai: 0.4603</p>				
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1413_44 Parent: CACHE_1413_21 distance_to_pai: 0.5647</p>				

Tested analogs

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1413_5

$K_D = 14 \mu\text{M}$ – 34% binding

DLS (solub@200 μM)

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

$\text{IC}_{50_ATPase} > 100 \mu\text{M}$

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1413_45 Parent CACHE_1413_5 distance_to_pai 0.2762</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1413_46 Parent CACHE_1413_5 distance_to_pai 0.4013</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1413_47 Parent CACHE_1413_5 distance_to_pai 0.576</p>
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1413_48 Parent CACHE_1413_5 distance_to_pai 0.5825</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1413_49 Parent CACHE_1413_5 distance_to_pai 0.5848</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1413_50 Parent CACHE_1413_5 distance_to_pai 0.5868</p>

Round 1 HIT MOLECULE

CACHE_1413_41

$K_D = 91 \mu\text{M}$ – 82% binding

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 8

No compound in Round 2

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2
Participant 1414

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1414_34

$K_D = 159 \mu\text{M}$ – 75% binding
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 2

10 analogs of CACHE_1414_34 were submitted for round 2.
1 compound (re-supplied parent molecule) confirmed binding by SPR, showing a tendency to reach saturation.

CACHE2-HO_1414_1

$K_D = 182 \mu\text{M}$ – 82% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@50 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1414_34

$K_D = 159 \mu\text{M}$ – 75% binding
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 2

Blank means inactive

Tested analogs

<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_1 Parent: CACHE_1414_34 distance_to_pai: 0</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_2 Parent: CACHE_1414_34 distance_to_pai: 0.112</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_3 Parent: CACHE_1414_34 distance_to_pai: 0.112</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_4 Parent: CACHE_1414_34 distance_to_pai: 0.1633</p>
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_5 Parent: CACHE_1414_34 distance_to_pai: 0.28</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_6 Parent: CACHE_1414_34 distance_to_pai: 0.428</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_7 Parent: CACHE_1414_34 distance_to_pai: 0.44</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_8 Parent: CACHE_1414_34 distance_to_pai: 0.5161</p>
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_9 Parent: CACHE_1414_34 distance_to_pai: 0.5292</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_10 Parent: CACHE_1414_34 distance_to_pai: 0.6281</p>		

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1414_40

$K_D = 33 \mu\text{M}$ – 77% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 10

24 analogs of CACHE_1414_40 were submitted for round 2.
 3 compounds showed a binding response by SPR.

CACHE2-HO_1414_13

$K_D_1 = 41 \mu\text{M}$ – 66% binding
 $K_D_2 = 56 \mu\text{M}$ – 45% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

CACHE2-HO_1414_14

K_D (3% DMSO) = 14 μM – 37% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 5

CACHE2-HO_1414_20

$K_D_1 = 36 \mu\text{M}$ – 62% binding
 K_D_2 (3% DMSO) = 27 μM – 49% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 8

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1414_40

$K_D = 33 \mu\text{M}$ – 77% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 10

Tested analogs

<p>not advanced to dose-response</p> <p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_14 Parent: CACHE_1414_40 distance_to_pai: 0.2121</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_18 Parent: CACHE_1414_40 distance_to_pai: 0.2754</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1414_22 Parent: CACHE_1414_40 distance_to_pai: 0.3161</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1414_40

$K_D = 33 \mu\text{M}$ – 77% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 10

Tested analogs (cont...)

<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1414_26 CACHE_1414_40 0.3478</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1414_30 CACHE_1414_40 0.3744</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1414_34 CACHE_1414_40 0.6426</p>			

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2

Participant 1418

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1418_68

$K_D = 25 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit/solubility issues) – 100 %binding
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 3$

6 analogs of CACHE_1418_68 were submitted for round 2. 1 of them showed a super stoichiometric binding to NSP13 in addition to weak non-selective binding to the unrelated protein WDR5.

CACHE2-HO_1418_34

$K_D_1 = 61 \mu\text{M}$ – 298 %binding

$K_D_2 = 74 \mu\text{M}$ – 336 %binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – weak binding

DLS (solub/no aggreg@200 μM)

%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 6$

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1418_68

$K_D = 25 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit/solubility issues) – 100 %binding
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 3$

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pare</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1418_33 CACHE_1418_68 0.2056</p>		
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pare</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1418_36 CACHE_1418_68 0.5714</p>		

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1418_3

K_D (3% DMSO) = 28 μM (solubility issues) – 93% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 14

11 analogs of CACHE_1418_3 were submitted for round 2 including the re-supplied parent molecule. The Re-supplied hit confirmed dose dependent binding to NSP13.

CACHE2-HO_1418_1

K_D (3% DMSO) = 21 μM (solubility issues) – 65% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 13

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1418_3

K_D (3% DMSO) = 28 μM (solubility issues) – 93% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 14

Tested analogs

Dose response: Confirmed								
	CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa	CACHE2-HO_1418_3 CACJE_1418_3 0.343						
	CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa	CACHE2-HO_1418_6 CACJE_1418_3 0.3615						
	CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa	CACHE2-HO_1418_9 CACJE_1418_3 0.3727						
	CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa	CACHE2-HO_1418_11 CACJE_1418_3 0.3929						

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1418_52

$K_D = 30 \mu\text{M}$ – 118% binding
WDR5 selectivity – 15% binding
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no inhibition

9 analogs of CACHE_1418_52 were submitted for round 2.
1 of them showed clear dose dependent binding response by SPR.

CACHE2-HO_1418_22

$K_D = 14 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 80% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 19

CACHE2-HO_1418_28

$K_{D_1} = 56 \mu\text{M}$ – 781% binding
 $K_{D_2} = 53 \mu\text{M}$ – 245% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 21

CACHE2-HO_1418_26

$K_D = 48 \mu\text{M}$ – 118% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 15

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1418_52

$K_D = 30 \mu\text{M}$ – 118% binding
 WDR5 selectivity – 15% binding
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no inhibition

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1418_24 Parent CACHE_1418_52 distance_to_par 0.3365</p>		
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1418_27 Parent CACHE_1418_52 distance_to_par 0.4236</p>		
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1418_30 Parent CACHE_1418_52 distance_to_par 0.5293</p>		

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1418_37

$K_D = 35 \mu\text{M}$ – 89% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 72%
Not confirmed by dose response $IC_{50} > 150$

6 analogs of CACHE_1418_37 were submitted for round 2.
1 of them (re-supplied parent molecule) confirmed a selective dose dependent binding response.

CACHE2-HO_1418_15

K_D (3% DMSO) = 35 μM – 54% binding
At 100 μM concentration shows binding to the reference cell
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 16

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1418_37

$K_D = 35 \mu\text{M}$ – 89% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 72%
 Not confirmed by dose response $IC_{50} > 150$

Tested analogs

Dose
 response:
 Confirmed

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1418_15
 Parent CACHE_1418_37
 distance_to_pai 0

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1418_16
 Parent CACHE_1418_37
 distance_to_pai 0.413

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1418_17
 Parent CACHE_1418_37
 distance_to_pai 0.4329

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1418_18
 Parent CACHE_1418_37
 distance_to_pai 0.5167

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1418_19
 Parent CACHE_1418_37
 distance_to_pai 0.5587

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1418_20
 Parent CACHE_1418_37
 distance_to_pai 0.5752

Round 1 HIT MOLECULE

CACHE_1418_6

$K_D = 45 \mu\text{M}$ – 42% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 5

Round 1 HIT MOLECULE

CACHE_1418_39

$K_D = 7 \mu\text{M}$ (**poor fit**) – 67% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 6

No analogs in Round 2

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2
Participant 1419

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1419_42

$K_D = 18 \mu\text{M}$ – 39% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – 67% binding
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 3

48 analogs of CACHE_1419_42 were submitted for round 2.
5 compounds including re-supplied parent molecule showed a binding response by SPR.

CACHE2-HO_1419_18

$K_D = 33 \mu\text{M}$ – 128% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub/@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

CACHE2-HO_1419_30

$K_D = 41 \mu\text{M}$ – 133% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 14

CACHE2-HO_1419_1

$K_D = 14 \mu\text{M}$ – 54% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – 16% binding
DLS (solub@100 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 8

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1419_42

$K_D = 18 \mu\text{M}$ – 39% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – 67% binding
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 3

CACHE2-HO_1419_28

$K_D_1 = 41 \mu\text{M}$ – 82% binding
 $K_D_2 = 17 \mu\text{M}$ – 85% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 14

CACHE2-HO_1419_29

$K_D_1 = 51 \mu\text{M}$ – 157% binding
 $K_D_2 = 55 \mu\text{M}$ – 177% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 13

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1419_42

$K_D = 18 \mu\text{M}$ – 39% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – 67% binding
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 3

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1419_4 Parent: CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai: 0.2262</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1419_8 Parent: CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai: 0.3061</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1419_12 Parent: CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai: 0.3415</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1419_16 Parent: CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai: 0.3574</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1419_42

$K_D = 18 \mu\text{M}$ – 39% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – 67% binding
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 3

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1419_20 Parent CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai 0.368</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1419_24 Parent CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai 0.4302</p>			
<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1419_28 Parent CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai 0.4613</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1419_32 Parent CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai 0.4725</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1419_42

$K_D = 18 \mu\text{M}$ – 39% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – 67% binding
 %inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 3$

Tested analogs

 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1419_36 Parent CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai 0.4983			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1419_40 Parent CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai 0.527			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1419_44 Parent CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai 0.578			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1419_48 Parent CACHE_1419_42 distance_to_pai 0.6113			

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2

Participant 1421

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1421_62

$K_D = 61 \mu\text{M}$ – 62% binding

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 13

11 analogs of CACHE_1421_62 were submitted for round 2.
2 compounds confirmed a selective dose dependent binding response by SPR.

CACHE2-HO_1421_29

K_D (3%DMSO) = 20 μM – 93% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

DLS (solub@200 μM)

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = -5

CACHE2-HO_1421_27

K_D (3% DMSO) = 19 μM (poor fit) – 101% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

DLS (solub@200 μM)

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = -5

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1421_62

$K_D = 61 \mu\text{M}$ – 62% binding

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 13

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1421_30 Parent CACHE_1421_62 distance_to_pai 0.2404</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1421_34 Parent CACHE_1421_62 distance_to_pai 0.2971</p>			
<p>Low solubility</p> <p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1421_37 Parent CACHE_1421_62 distance_to_pai 0.3412</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1421_1

$K_D = 26 \mu\text{M}$ – 65% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 14$

9 analogs of CACHE_1421_1 were submitted for round 2.
1 compound showed a superstoichiometric binding response with mild binding affinity to unrelated negative control protein.

CACHE2-HO_1421_3

$K_D_1 = 104 \mu\text{M}$ – 395% binding
 $K_D_2 = 98 \mu\text{M}$ – 393% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – mild binding
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 40$

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1421_1

$K_D = 26 \mu\text{M}$ – 65% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 14

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1421_4 Parent CACHE_1421_1 distance_to_pai 0.2593</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1421_8 Parent CACHE_1421_1 distance_to_pai 0.4177</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1421_9 Parent CACHE_1421_1 distance_to_pai 0.4244</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1421_21

$K_D = 11 \mu\text{M}$ – 74% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@100 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 12

14 analogs of CACHE_1421_21 were submitted for round 2.
2 compound showed a binding response.

CACHE2-HO_1421_16

$K_D = 30 \mu\text{M}$ – 122% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 13

CACHE2-HO_1421_12

K_D (3% DMSO) = 43 μM – 60% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@100 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 16

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1421_21

$K_D = 11 \mu\text{M}$ – 74% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@100 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 12

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1421_13 CACHE_1421_21 0.04219</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1421_17 CACHE_1421_21 0.252</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1421_21 CACHE_1421_21 0.3677</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1421_23 CACHE_1421_21 0.4211</p>			

Tested analogs

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1421_33

$K_D = 18 \mu\text{M}$ – 73% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – 25% binding

DLS (solub@200 μM)

%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 86$

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1421_24
 Parent CACHE_1421_33
 distance_to_parent 0.2322

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1421_25
 Parent CACHE_1421_33
 distance_to_parent 0.2358

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1421_26
 Parent CACHE_1421_33
 distance_to_parent 0.2857

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2
Participant 1422

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1422_15

$K_D = 85 \mu\text{M}$ – 91% binding
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 IC_{50_1} ATPase = 39 μM , Hill slope -1.2
 IC_{50_2} ATPase = 96 μM , Hill slope -0.7
 IC_{50} no DNA _ ATPase = 43 μM , Hill slope -1.0

36 analogs of CACHE_1422_15 were submitted for round 2.
 2 compounds showed a binding response by SPR with a tendency to saturation.

CACHE2-HO_1422_6

$K_D = 128 \mu\text{M}$ (baseline difference) – 238% binding
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

CACHE2-HO_1422_13

$K_D_1 = 41 \mu\text{M}$ – 110% binding
 $K_D_2 = 33 \mu\text{M}$ – 120% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 6

CACHE2-HO_1422_23

$K_D = 19 \mu\text{M}$ – 73% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@100 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1422_15

$K_D = 85 \mu\text{M}$ – 91% binding

DLS (solub@200 μM)

IC_{50_1} ATPase = 39 μM , Hill slope -1.2

IC_{50_2} ATPase = 96 μM , Hill slope -0.7

IC_{50} no DNA _ ATPase = 43 μM , Hill slope -1.0

Tested analogs

Bad sensorgram				
	CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa	CACHE2-HO_1422_1 CACHE_1422_15 0		CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa
				CACHE2-HO_1422_2 CACHE_1422_15 0.2364
	CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa	CACHE2-HO_1422_3 CACHE_1422_15 0.2445		CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa
				CACHE2-HO_1422_4 CACHE_1422_15 0.2463
	CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa	CACHE2-HO_1422_5 CACHE_1422_15 0.2617		CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa
				CACHE2-HO_1422_6 CACHE_1422_15 0.2652
	CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa	CACHE2-HO_1422_7 CACHE_1422_15 0.2675		CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa
				CACHE2-HO_1422_8 CACHE_1422_15 0.2796
	CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa	CACHE2-HO_1422_9 CACHE_1422_15 0.2816		CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa
				CACHE2-HO_1422_10 CACHE_1422_15 0.2835
	CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa	CACHE2-HO_1422_11 CACHE_1422_15 0.2849		CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa
				CACHE2-HO_1422_12 CACHE_1422_15 0.2866

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1422_15

$K_D = 85 \mu\text{M}$ – 91% binding

DLS (solub@200 μM)

IC_{50_1} ATPase = 39 μM , Hill slope -1.2

IC_{50_2} ATPase = 96 μM , Hill slope -0.7

IC_{50} no DNA _ ATPase = 43 μM , Hill slope -1.0

Tested analogs

<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1422_16 Parent: CACHE_1422_15 distance_to_pai: 0.3252</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1422_20 Parent: CACHE_1422_15 distance_to_pai: 0.3872</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1422_24 Parent: CACHE_1422_15 distance_to_pai: 0.3918</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1422_15

$K_D = 85 \mu\text{M}$ – 91% binding

DLS (solub@200 μM)

IC_{50_1} ATPase = 39 μM , Hill slope -1.2

IC_{50_2} ATPase = 96 μM , Hill slope -0.7

IC_{50} no DNA _ ATPase = 43 μM , Hill slope -1.0

Tested analogs

 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1422_28 Parent CACHE_1422_15 distance_to_pai 0.419			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1422_32 Parent CACHE_1422_15 distance_to_pai 0.4378			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1422_36 Parent CACHE_1422_15 distance_to_pai 0.478			

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2
Participant 1425

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1425_80

$K_D = 19 \mu\text{M}$ (baseline difference/poor fit) – 95% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no inhibition

12 follow-ups of CACHE_1425_80 were submitted for round 2.
1 compound showed a mild binding response reaching saturation.

CACHE2-HO_1425_9

$K_D = 15 \mu\text{M}$ – 44% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 10

¹⁹F NMR
Did not confirm binding

Black = 10 uM compound
Red = 10 uM compound, 20 uM NSP13

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1425_80

$K_D = 19 \mu\text{M}$ (baseline difference/poor fit) – 95% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no inhibition

Tested follow-ups

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1425_4 Parent CACHE_1425_80 distance_to_pai 0.5594</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1425_8 Parent CACHE_1425_80 distance_to_pai 0.607</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1425_12 Parent CACHE_1425_80 distance_to_pai 0.6989</p>			

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2
Participant 1430

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1430_25

$K_D = 22 \mu\text{M}$ (solubility issues) – 81% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
 $IC_{50_ATPase} > 100 \mu\text{M}$

48 analogs of CACHE_1430_25 were submitted for round 2.
3 compounds showed a weak binding response by SPR.

CACHE2-HO_1430_1

K_D (3%DMSO) = 6 μM (poor fit) – 29% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@100 μM)
%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M_ATPase}$ = 11

CACHE2-HO_1430_16

$K_D = 122 \mu\text{M}$ – 133% binding
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M_ATPase}$ = 25

CACHE2-HO_1430_33

K_D (3% DMSO) = 36 μM (baseline difference) – 121% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M_ATPase}$ = 10

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1430_25

$K_D = 22 \mu\text{M}$ (solubility issues) – 81% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 $IC_{50_ATPase} > 100 \mu\text{M}$

Tested analogs

<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_1 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_2 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.01749</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_3 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.04274</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_4 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.04651</p>
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_5 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.07042</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_6 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.1444</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_7 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.1519</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_8 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.1738</p>
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_9 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.1771</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_10 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.1782</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_11 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.1933</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_12 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.2039</p>
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_13 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.2082</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_14 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.2087</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_15 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.2089</p>	<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_16 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.2105</p>

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1430_25

$K_D = 22 \mu\text{M}$ (solubility issues) – 81% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 $IC_{50_ATPase} > 100 \mu\text{M}$

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_36 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.3449</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_40 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.3636</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_44 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.3955</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1430_48 Parent CACHE_1430_25 distance_to_pai 0.4574</p>			

Round 1 HIT MOLECULE

CACHE_1430_47

K_D = 144 μ M (does not reach saturation) – 125% binding

DLS (solub@100 μ M)

%inhibition@50 μ M_ATPase = 91

No analog in Round 2

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2

Participant 1431

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1431_64

$K_D = 85 \mu\text{M}$ – 111% binding
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 9

11 non-analog follow-ups of CACHE_1431_64 were submitted for round 2. One compound showed a high binding affinity by SPR that was confirmed by ^{19}F NMR.

Black = 10 uM compound
Red = 10 uM compound, 20 uM NSP13

CACHE2-HO_1431_6

$K_D_{-1} = 0.65 \mu\text{M}$ – 72% binding
 K_D_{-2} (3% DMSO) = $0.9 \mu\text{M}$ – 51% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@100 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

Confirmed!

^{19}F NMR

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1431_64

$K_D = 85 \mu\text{M}$ – 111% binding
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 9

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1431_4 Parent CACHE_1431_64 distance_to_pai 0.6849</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1431_8 Parent CACHE_1431_64 distance_to_pai 0.7225</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1431_11 Parent CACHE_1431_64 distance_to_pai 0.7686</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1431_96

$K_D = 46 \mu\text{M}$ (slow on/off)– 124% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – mild binding to WDR5
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 18

Resupply – showed baseline difference
and was not included for a dose -
response

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2
Participant 1434

Round 1 HIT MOLECULE

CACHE_1434_50

$K_D = 140 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 39% binding
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no binding

Round 1 HIT MOLECULE

CACHE_1434_57

$K_D = 22 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit/low binding) – 24% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 2

No analogs in Round 2

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2
Participant 1438

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1438_39

$K_D = 9 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 84% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 8

45 analogs of CACHE_1438_39 were submitted for round 2.

4 compounds (including re-supplied parent molecule) showed a binding response by SPR with a tendency to reach saturation. 1 compound confirmed binding affinity by ^{19}F NMR.

Black = 10 μM compound
Red = 10 μM compound, 20 μM NSP13

^{19}F NMR

CACHE2-HO_1438_19

$K_{D_1} = 90 \mu\text{M}$ – 166% binding
 $K_{D_2} = 80 \mu\text{M}$ – 198% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1438_39

$K_D = 9 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 84% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 8$

CACHE2-HO_1438_1

K_D (3% DMSO) = 124 μM (does not reach saturation) – 268% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – 31% binding (linear response)
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 11$

CACHE2-HO_1438_3

$K_D = 78 \mu\text{M}$ – 178% binding
 Suspicious sensorgram
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = -3$

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1438_39

$K_D = 9 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 84% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 8

CACHE2-HO_1438_22

$K_D = 49 \mu\text{M}$ – 102% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) –
weak binding (linear response)
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 10

CACHE2-HO_1438_41

$K_D = 64 \mu\text{M}$ – 81% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 8

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1438_39

$K_D = 9 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 84% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 8

Tested analogs

 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1438_5 Parent CACHE_1438_39 distance_to_pi: 0.1292				
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1438_10 Parent CACHE_1438_39 distance_to_pi: 0.214				
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1438_15 Parent CACHE_1438_39 distance_to_pi: 0.2734				
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1438_20 Parent CACHE_1438_39 distance_to_pi: 0.3404				

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1438_39

$K_D = 9 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 84% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 8

Tested analogs

 Cache ID CACHE2-HO_1438_25 Parent CACHE_1438_39 distance_to_p: 0.4007				
 Cache ID CACHE2-HO_1438_30 Parent CACHE_1438_39 distance_to_p: 0.4363				
 Cache ID CACHE2-HO_1438_35 Parent CACHE_1438_39 distance_to_p: 0.4585				
 Cache ID CACHE2-HO_1438_40 Parent CACHE_1438_39 distance_to_p: 0.4946				
 Cache ID CACHE2-HO_1438_45 Parent CACHE_1438_39 distance to p: 0.6266				

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2
Participant 1439

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1439_43

$K_D = 12 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 49% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

18 analogues of CACHE_1439_43, including re-supplied parent molecule, were submitted for round 2.

Re-supplied hit showed a weak dose dependent binding response.

CACHE2-HO_1439_21

K_D (3% DMSO) = 11 μM (low binding) – 26% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 32

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1439_43

$K_D = 12 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 49% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

Tested follow-ups

 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1439_24 Parent CACHE_1439_43 distance_to_pai 0.4985			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1439_28 Parent CACHE_1439_43 distance_to_pai 0.5757			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1439_32 Parent CACHE_1439_43 distance_to_pai 0.6216			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1439_43

$K_D = 12 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 49% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

Tested follow-ups

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1439_36 Parent CACHE_1439_43 distance_to_pai 0.6553</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1439_40 Parent CACHE_1439_43 distance_to_pai 0.6898</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1439_44 Parent CACHE_1439_43 distance_to_pai 0.7068</p>			

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1439_45
 Parent CACHE_1439_43
 distance_to_pai 0.7084

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1439_26

$K_D = 147 \mu\text{M}$ – 127% binding

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no binding

Tested follow-ups

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1439_38

$K_D = 114 \mu\text{M}$ – 124% binding

DLS (solub@200 μM)

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

Tested follow-ups

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1439_7 Parent CACHE_1439_38 distance_to_pa 0.4772</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1439_11 Parent CACHE_1439_38 distance_to_pa 0.5969</p>			

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2

Participant 1442

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1442_89

$K_D = 50 \mu\text{M}$ – 41% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@100 μM)
 $IC_{50_ATPase} > 100 \mu\text{M}$

36 analogues of CACHE_1442_89, including re-supplied parent molecule, were submitted for round 2.

Re-supplied hit showed a weak dose dependent binding response.

CACHE2-HO_1442_1

$K_D = 24 \mu\text{M}$ (poor fit) – 35% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M_ATPase} = 18$

Tested follow-ups

Round 1 HIT MOLECULE

CACHE_1442_89

$K_D = 50 \mu\text{M}$ – 41% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@100 μM)
 $IC_{50_ATPase} > 100 \mu\text{M}$

<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_1 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_2 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.09643</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_3 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.3245</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_4 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.3536</p>
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_5 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.4033</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_6 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.4088</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_7 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.413</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_8 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.4152</p>
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_9 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.4167</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_10 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.4189</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_11 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.4207</p>	<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_12 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.4223</p>

Tested follow-ups

Round 1 HIT MOLECULE

CACHE_1442_89

$K_D = 50 \mu\text{M}$ – 41% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@100 μM)
 $IC_{50_ATPase} > 100 \mu\text{M}$

 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_16 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.4269			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_20 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.4377			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_24 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.4441			

Tested follow-ups

Round 1 HIT MOLECULE

CACHE_1442_89

$K_D = 50 \mu\text{M}$ – 41% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@100 μM)
 $IC_{50_ATPase} > 100 \mu\text{M}$

 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_32 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.5632			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_36 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.6335			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1442_40 Parent CACHE_1442_89 distance_to_pai 0.6692			

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2
Participant 1448

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1448_70

$K_D = 51 \mu\text{M}$ – 76% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 1

44 analogs of CACHE_1448_70 were submitted for round 2.
3 compounds (including re-supplied parent molecule) showed a dose dependent binding response by SPR.

CACHE2-HO_1448_1

K_D (3% DMSO) = 82 μM – 123% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 9

CACHE2-HO_1448_8

$K_D = 26 \mu\text{M}$ – 66% binding
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 6

CACHE2-HO_1448_29

$K_D = 54 \mu\text{M}$ – 49% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 6

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1448_70

KD = 51 μ M – 76% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

%inhibition@50 μ M_ATPase = 1

Tested analogs

<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_1 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_2 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.01258</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_3 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.01258</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_4 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.03086</p>
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_5 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.03681</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_6 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.05988</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_7 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.07927</p>	<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_8 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.07927</p>
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_9 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.08485</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_10 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.09036</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_11 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.09357</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_12 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.09434</p>
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_13 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.1092</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_14 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.1105</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_15 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.1136</p>	<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1448_16 Parent: CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai: 0.1395</p>

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1448_70

KD = 51 μ M – 76% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

%inhibition@50 μ M_ATPase = 1

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1448_20 CACHE_1448_70 0.1705</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1448_24 CACHE_1448_70 0.191</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1448_28 CACHE_1448_70 0.228</p>			
<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pa</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1448_32 CACHE_1448_70 0.2929</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1448_70

KD = 51 μ M – 76% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

%inhibition@50 μ M_ATPase = 1

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1448_36 Parent CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai 0.3239</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1448_40 Parent CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai 0.3856</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1448_44 Parent CACHE_1448_70 distance_to_pai 0.5292</p>			

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2

Participant 1451

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1451_96

$K_D = 36 \mu\text{M}$ – 42% binding
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 $\text{IC}_{50_ATPase} = 24 \mu\text{M}$

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1451_4 CACHE_1451_96 0.1627</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1451_8 CACHE_1451_96 0.2831</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1451_12 CACHE_1451_96 0.3079</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1451_96

$K_D = 36 \mu\text{M}$ – 42% binding

DLS (solub@200 μM)

$IC_{50_ATPase} = 24 \mu\text{M}$

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1451_16 CACHE_1451_96 0.3514</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pai</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1451_18 CACHE_1451_96 0.5351</p>			

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2
Participant 1454

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_20

$K_D = 64 \mu\text{M}$ (does not reach saturation) – 89% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 $IC_{50_ATPase} > 160 \mu\text{M}$

8 analogs of CACHE_1454_20 were submitted for round 2. The re-supplied parent molecule confirmed a selective binding response by SPR and by ^{19}F NMR.

CACHE2-HO_1454_15

$K_{D_1} = 31 \mu\text{M}$ – 53% binding
 $K_{D_2} = 30 \mu\text{M}$ – 68% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M_ATPase} = 21$

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_20

$K_D = 64 \mu\text{M}$ (does not reach saturation) – 89% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 $IC_{50_ATPase} > 160 \mu\text{M}$

Tested analogs

<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_17 Parent CACHE_1454_20 distance_to_parent 0.344</p>		
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_20 Parent CACHE_1454_20 distance_to_parent 0.4152</p>		
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_22 Parent CACHE_1454_20 distance_to_parent 0.5123</p>		

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_98

$K_D = 25 \mu\text{M}$ (solubility issues) – 69% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – 26% binding
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM_ATPase = 1

7 analogs of CACHE_1454_98 were submitted for round 2. 2 compound (including re-supplied parent molecule) showed a dose dependent binding response by SPR with a tendency to reach saturation.

CACHE2-HO_1454_44

$K_D = 65 \mu\text{M}$ (solubility issues) – 107% binding
%inhibition@50 μM_ATPase = 8

CACHE2-HO_1454_45

$K_{D_1} = 44 \mu\text{M}$ – 135% binding
 $K_{D_2} = 50 \mu\text{M}$ – 155% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM_ATPase = 11

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_98

$K_D = 25 \mu\text{M}$ (solubility issues) – 69% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – 26% binding
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 1

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1454_47 Parent: CACHE_1454_98 distance_to_parent: 0.3406</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID: CACHE2-HO_1454_50 Parent: CACHE_1454_98 distance_to_parent: 0.4096</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_13

$K_D = 84 \mu\text{M}$ – 141% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 13

6 analogs of CACHE_1454_13 were submitted for round 2. The re-supplied parent molecule confirmed a selective dose dependent binding response with a tendency to reach saturation.

CACHE2-HO_1454_1

$K_D_1 = 92 \mu\text{M}$ – 111% binding
 $K_D_2 = 60 \mu\text{M}$ – 98% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 5

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_13

$K_D = 84 \mu\text{M}$ – 141% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 7

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_par</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1454_3 CACHE_1454_13 0.3084</p>		
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_par</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1454_6 CACHE_1454_13 0.4017</p>		

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_91

$K_D = 64 \mu\text{M}$ – 55% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 1

23 analogs of CACHE_1454_91 were submitted for round 2. 2 compound (including re-supplied parent molecule) confirmed a selective dose dependent binding response with a tendency to reach saturation.

CACHE2-HO_1454_38

$K_D = 55 \mu\text{M}$ – 86% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 9

CACHE2-HO_1454_36

K_D (3% DMSO) = 88 μM - 127% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 10

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_91

$K_D = 64 \mu\text{M}$ – 55% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 1

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_40 Parent CACHE_1454_91 distance_to_pa 0.3153</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_42 Parent CACHE_1454_91 distance_to_pa 0.3398</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_26 Parent CACHE_1454_91 distance_to_pa 0.5174</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_91

$K_D = 64 \mu\text{M}$ – 55% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 1$

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_3 Parent CACHE_1454_91 distance_to_pa 0.5638</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_6 Parent CACHE_1454_91 distance_to_pa 0.5931</p>			
<p>Dose response: Confirmed CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_36 Parent CACHE_1454_91 distance_to_pa 0.6</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_46

$K_D = 17 \mu\text{M}$ – 58% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no inhibition

6 analogs of CACHE_1454_46 were submitted for round 2.
2 compounds confirmed a selective dose dependent binding response by SPR.

CACHE2-HO_1454_25

$K_D_1 = 43 \mu\text{M}$ – 69% binding
 $K_D_2 = 65 \mu\text{M}$ – 95% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 14

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_46

$K_D = 17 \mu\text{M}$ – 58% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no inhibition

Tested analogs

<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pare</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1454_25 CACHE_1454_46 0.392</p> <p>Dose response: Confirmed</p>		
<p>CACHE_ID Parent distance_to_pare</p> <p>CACHE2-HO_1454_28 CACHE_1454_46 0.511</p>		

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_19

$K_D = 79 \mu\text{M}$ – 100% binding
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no inhibition

5 analogs of CACHE_1454_19 were submitted for round 2. Re-supplied parent molecule confirmed a selective dose dependent binding response by SPR.

CACHE2-HO_1454_7

$K_D = 102 \mu\text{M}$ – 98% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 11

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_19

$K_D = 79 \mu\text{M}$ – 100% binding

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no inhibition

Tested analogs

<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_9 Parent CACHE_1454_19 distance_to_parent 0.1858</p>		
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_11 Parent CACHE_1454_19 distance_to_parent 0.2374</p>		

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_61

$K_D = 5 \mu\text{M}$ – 36% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

DLS (solub@100 μM)

$IC_{50_ATPase} = 29 \mu\text{M}$

Tested analogs

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_75

$K_D = 47 \mu\text{M}$ (slow on/off) – 106% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 1

7 analogs of CACHE_1454_75 were submitted for round 2.

2 compounds showed a selective dose dependent binding response by SPR.

CACHE2-HO_1454_33

K_D (3% DMSO) = 99 μM (does not reach saturation/solubility issue) – 209% binding
 DLS(solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 14

CACHE2-HO_1454_36

K_D (3% DMSO) = 88 μM – 127% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS(solub@200 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 10

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1454_75

$K_D = 47 \mu\text{M}$ (slow on/off) – 106% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 1

Tested analogs

 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_34 Parent CACHE_1454_75 distance_to_pai 0.3561			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1454_37 Parent CACHE_1454_75 distance_to_pai 0.4385			

CACHE#2 – NSP13 SARS2

Participant 1456

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1456_73

$K_D = 45 \mu\text{M}$ – 88% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no inhibition

16 analogs of CACHE_1456_73 were submitted for round 2.
2 compound showed a dose dependent binding response by SPR.

CACHE2-HO_1456_42

$K_D_1 = 36 \mu\text{M}$ – 65% binding
 $K_D_2 = 29 \mu\text{M}$ – 68% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 9

CACHE2-HO_1456_26

$K_D = 86 \mu\text{M}$ – 116% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 19

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1456_73

$K_D = 45 \mu\text{M}$ – 88% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no inhibition

Black = 10 μM compound
Red = 10 μM compound, 30 μM NSP13

Unconvincing or
weak binding

^{19}F NMR

CACHE2-HO_1456_26

$K_D = 86 \mu\text{M}$ – 116% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 19

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1456_73

$K_D = 45 \mu\text{M}$ – 88% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = no inhibition

Tested analogs

 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_41 Parent CACHE_1456_73 distance_to_pa 0.2416			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_44 Parent CACHE_1456_73 distance_to_pa 0.383			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_13 Parent CACHE_1456_73 distance_to_pa 0.4593			
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_25 Parent CACHE_1456_73 distance_to_pa 0.482			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1456_57

$K_D = 12 \mu\text{M}$ – 43% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@100 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 59%, upon retesting was 31%

11 analogs of CACHE_1456_57 were submitted for round 2.
1 compound showed a binding response reaching saturation.

CACHE2-HO_1456_32

$K_D = 22 \mu\text{M}$ – 52% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 24

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1456_57

$K_D = 12 \mu\text{M}$ – 43% binding
 Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
 DLS (solub@100 μM)
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 59%, upon retesting was 31%

Tested analogs

 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_29 Parent CACHE_1456_57 distance_to_parent 0.07805		
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_32 Parent CACHE_1456_57 distance_to_parent 0.1215		
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_35 Parent CACHE_1456_57 distance_to_parent 0.1449		
 CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_37 Parent CACHE_1456_57 distance_to_parent 0.1721		

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1456_38

$K_D = 6 \mu\text{M}$ – 52% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 20

12 analogs of CACHE_1456_38, including the re-supplied hit molecule, were submitted for round 2.

1 compound (re-supplied parent molecule) confirmed weak binding by SPR, reaching saturation.

CACHE2-HO_1456_8

$K_D = 19 \mu\text{M}$ – 30% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – 10% binding
 $IC_{50_ATPase} > 100 \mu\text{M}$

Tested analogs

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1456_38

$K_D = 6 \mu\text{M}$ – 52% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

DLS (solub@200 μM)

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 20

Weak binding confirmed

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_8
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_9
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0.1759

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_10
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0.181

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_11
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0.1883

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_12
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0.1928

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_13
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0.1953

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_14
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0.2124

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_15
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0.2298

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_16
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0.2302

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_17
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0.3322

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_18
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0.3559

CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_19
Parent CACHE_1456_38
distance_to_pa 0.3733

Tested analogs

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1456_37

$K_D = 43 \mu\text{M}$ – 71% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – mild binding

DLS (solub@200 μM)

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 16

<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_4 Parent CACHE_1456_37 distance_to_pa 0.2871</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_7 Parent CACHE_1456_37 distance_to_pa 0.3431</p>			

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1456_42

$K_D = 95 \mu\text{M}$ (does not reach saturation) – 59% binding
aggreg@200 μM
%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 12$

7 analogs of CACHE_1456_42 were submitted for round 2. 2 compounds (including re-supplied parent molecule) showed a dose dependent binding response with a tendency to reach saturation.

CACHE2-HO_1456_20

$K_D = 139 \mu\text{M}$ – 88% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 13$

CACHE2-HO_1456_26

$K_D = 86 \mu\text{M}$ – 117% binding
Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes
DLS (solub@200 μM)
%inhibition@50 $\mu\text{M}_{\text{ATPase}} = 19$

PARENT MOLECULE

CACHE_1456_42

$K_D = 95 \mu\text{M}$ (does not reach saturation) – 59% binding
 aggreg@200 μM
 %inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 12

Tested analogs

<p>Dose response: Confirmed</p> <p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_23 Parent CACHE_1456_42 distance_to_pai 0.2182</p>			
<p>CACHE_ID CACHE2-HO_1456_26 Parent CACHE_1456_42 distance_to_pai 0.2451</p>			

Round 1 HIT MOLECULE

CACHE_1456_17

$K_D = 32 \mu\text{M}$ – 50% binding

Selectivity (unrelated WDR5 protein) – Yes

DLS (solub@200 μM)

%inhibition@50 μM _ATPase = 5

No analog in Round 2